

Creating Personas for NFDI x CS Project

Introduction

This document contains an overview of the second community development workshop of the NFDI x CS project. This appendix is an open access report that refers to a publication titled “Utilizing Personas to Create Infrastructures for Research Data and Software Management” at Hochschule 2034¹.

The persona workshop was held in February 2024 as part of the activities during the third plenary meeting of NFDI x CS at the GWDG in Göttingen. The goal was to create personas representing future users and stakeholders of the Research Data and Software Management (RDSM). In the first part of this community development series, the field of stakeholders was explored together and placative positive and negative statements about RDSM from the perspective of the stakeholder were collected. As a starting point for this workshop, these positive and negative statements were clustered into broader topics, such as Reputation and Visibility, Cultural Change, Know-How, Controlling Use of Research Output, Support Structures, Impact, and Resources (Time and Money). Based on these clusters, a statement was picked from each cluster and used for the creation of a persona.

The process of creating a persona involves developing an imaginary person who represents a member of the target group. This is supported by a predesigned questionnaire. The questionnaire helps to create an imaginary CV, design the look of the persona, and highlight the experiences with RDSM services. Specifically for the RDSM section, it was necessary to create two versions of the questionnaire: one for academics and another for non-academics, including policymakers, industry professionals, and members of society.

The personas are designed to explore the user context for services within the NFDI x CS community and for intersections with other communities. The resulting personas can be used for different tasks:

1. Constructing and prioritizing requirements for activities, services, and architecture.
2. Communicating decisions to stakeholders.
3. Testing created activities from the perspective of the personas.

For example, one of the next steps involved using these personas to develop user stories and use cases based on the personas in different task areas.

The Personas Questionnaire

2.1 Background information

The persona questionnaire started with a general information. In the first part of the questionnaire, participants were asked to provide general background information about the functionary personas, as well as to list any memberships in associations, society or advisory boards, as shown in Table 1. They also asked to list three of the recent professional positions. This information was indeed needed to collect basic details about the persona, especially their field of study and research discipline.

Name		Gender	
Field of Study		Degree	
Research Disc.		Position	
Affiliation			
Memberships (associations, society, advisory boards)			

Table 1. Background Information of Persona

¹ <https://www.cs.uni-potsdam.de/hochschule2034/>

2.2 Creating the personality

In order to visualise the personas, participants were asked in the second part of the questionnaire to answer questions about the personas' interests, building their profiles and the goals related to their work.

Table 2 shows the design process followed for creating personality.

What does the person do in their free time? What are the interests of the person?	
	Hair colour
	Skin colour
	Fashion Style
	Glasses/contact lenses
	Jewelry
	Wearables
	Quote about RDSM

Table 2. Creating Personality of Persona

2.3 Intersection with RDSM

The main part of this questionnaire was about the persona experiences with RDSM. The participants were asked to provide successful or failure stories from their experiences in dealing with RDSM through their academic or non-academic carriers and research projects, as shown in table 3.

Does the person have experiences with RDSM? Are these experiences success (✓) or failure(✗) stories?	
	✓ ✗
	✓ ✗
	✓ ✗
	✓ ✗
What is the person trying to do with RDSM? Integrating good practices into his/her daily life, teach people about, create services,...?	
What could help to address this person in RDSM?	

Table 3. Persona's Intersection with RDSM (the academic version)

In the non-academic questionnaire, the focal point was on how RDSM are related to the organizational agenda to which they belong. The question also allowed for a description of any plans to integrate RDSM into the political agenda and standardization process as a long vision in the organisations: "How relevant is RDSM for personal or organisational agenda? The person wants to integrate Research Data/Software into a political agenda, use RDSM in research activities in industry, use results from a standardisation process?"

Academic and Non-Academic questionnaires ended with an open question to give all participants space to add any further details about the persona.

Personas Overview

In this workshop, nine personas were created in total: seven academic and two non-academic. Statistics show that most of the academic personas were holding Ph.D. degree, with only one holding a bachelor 's degree. Of the two non-academic personas, one held a Ph.D. and the other a master's degree. The table below shows the results.

Academic			Non-Academic		
Bachelor	Masters	Ph.D.	Bachelor	Masters	Ph.D.
1		6	0	1	1
7			2		

Table 4. Distribution of Academic and Non-Academic Personas

Each participant was asked to join one of the following clusters groups to design at least one persona (Academic or Non-Academic):

- Controlling the use of research output
- Cultural change
- Impact
- Know how
- Resource: Time and Money
- Support structure
- Reputation and visibility

Some participants managed to design personas for both categories. Table 5 provides an overview of the personas gathered from all groups.

SL	Name	Degree	Role	Cluster	Position	Quote about RDSM	Persona Overview
1	Peter Östdoc	Ph.D.	Academic	Controlling the use of research output	Postdoc	It distracts me from my research	needs incentives, such as conferences or advantages in applications for permanent positions, to prepare and publish his research data.
2	Dr. Napoleon Schmidt	Ph.D.	Academic	Cultural change	CIO	Always raise the privacy issue, not ready to sign off	doesn't see the need of changing anything in his institution.
3	Wim	Bachelor	Academic	Impact	MA student	Publishing research data can also be materially rewarding	due to the publication of her research data of her bachelorthesis she has gotten a job as a student assistant
4	Patricio Becker	Ph.D.	Academic	Know how	Scientific Assistant	Better Compliance	give people methods to use digital services

							for research data management
5	John Doe	Ph.D.	Academic	Resource: Time and Money	Postdoc		no intrinsic motivation, just wants to comply to requirements
6	Jenny Wong	Ph.D.	Academic	Support structure	Team Lead	This ensures/creates legal certainty	needs data and metadata to convince to politicians of necessary work for Nationalpark Eifel
7	Dr. Alex Kim	Ph.D.	Academic	Reputation and visibility	Team Cybersecurity Lead	Precision in research data management is as crucial as in coding for security. One flaw, and the system's integrity could be compromised.	wants to mentor people in her group about RDSM
8	Martin Frings	Magister	Non-academic	Support structure	City Council Monschau - Teacher High School	I need legal advice first	counterpart to Jenny Wong... will be only convinced to preserve the data if the argumentation is scientific grounded
9	Dr. Martin Schneider	Ph.D.	Non-academic	Reputation and visibility	Head of Data Compliance	In the interconnected world of automotive data, compliance is not just about following rules; it's about ensuring trust in every bite of data we collect and process.	advocates proactive data compliance strategies and systems

Table 5. Overview of Personas

Personas results

In the following provide the interested readers analysis about each the persona designed in the workshop

Persona: Peter Östdoc

- Holds a Ph.D
- HPC at TU Bielefeld
- Memberships: ACM, IEEE, GI & Peta
- RDSM Quote: It distracts me from my research.

- Academic goals: Permanent Position
- Success Story: Managing artifacts and the published with the challenge of data deadline-driven paper development.
- Failure Story: Dealing with large amounts of accumulated and un-structured/sorted data,
- With RDSM: sort, structure the data, and Find hidden secrets in data (energy consumption of individual TCP packets)
- Help to address RDSM:
 - Guarantee the storage capabilities of the RDSM system
 - provide Semantic services through the metadata searching process.
 - Adding value to the organization and research field where the data and metadata are clearly shown.

Persona: Napoleon Schmidt

- CIO and researcher in Data Privacy
- Memberships: Shepherd Association
- RDSM Quote: Always raise the privacy issue, not ready to sign off.
- Academic goals: Retiring without scandals
- Failure Story:
 - Better Compliance with own rules
 - Same mission, same goals as long as we stay in compliance
- With RDSM: doing good practices but pushing on everybody
- Help to address RDSM: learning to be supportive, but until now hopeless cause

Persona: Wim

- Master Student, Digital Humanities
- RDSM Quote: Publishing research data can also be materially rewarding.
- Academic goals: MA -> PhD -> Professorship in 8 years
- Success Story:
 - Getting human knowledge experience in RDC in publication, in the position in the library of the University.
 - Working on high-quality RD
- With RDSM:
 - Establish expert groups in RDSM management.
 - Structuring and enabling RDSM in another project, other projects produce RD and take care of those data/metadata in order and structure them in a suitable Repository.
- Help to address RDSM:
 - Finding like-minded people to build this network.
 - Seeking to offer services in RD infrastructure such as meta-data

Persona: Patricio Becker

- Holds a Ph.D in humanities
- Librarian, and researcher in Humanities at KIT
- Memberships: GI
- RDSM Quote: We need better Compliance
- Academic goals: Impact FAIR data usage
- Failure story: Cannot use the required data for his PhD research work
- With RDSM: Trying to find Methods on how to use digital services for data retrieval, and Raise awareness on data usage compliance.
- Help to address RDSM: Training material/guideline

Persona: John Doe

- Holds a Ph.D in Computer Science.

- Researcher in Computer Science (AI)
- Academic goals: Complete habilitation and publish more papers.
- Failure stories:
 - Pressure and competition in publishing papers, with no enough time for RDSM.
 - During PhD, tried to build a reproducible model, but the paper published took longer than usual.
- With RDSM: only tries to comply if there are requirements for RDSM.
- Help to address RDSM: Low-level entrance, and easy usage.

Persona: Jenny Wong

- Holds a Ph.D in Computational Biology.
- Team lead for Ecosystem Development at the Institute RWTH Aachen.
- Memberships: Involved in ISCB, which is the International Society for Computational Biology, and the Eifel National Park.
- RDSM Quote: This ensures/creates legal certainty.
- Academic goals: Becoming a professor
- Success Story: Artifact creation: Publication of data + analysis SW for nature journal
- Failure Story:
 - When I wanted to contribute an artifact to an important journal, I noticed that I had to show which and how I processed the data and which methods I used to evaluate the data to substantiate my findings It was totally new for me and a huge challenge.
 - The challenge is that different data comes out every time and then I choose a different grid and it's classified differently. I am convinced that this process step needs to be professionalized.
- With RDSM: Consensing politicians in her role as advisor Eifel National Park.
- Help to address RDSM: Version management of GIS data, and established metadata formats for GIS data.

Persona: Alex Kim

- Holds a Ph.D in Computer Science.
- Cybersecurity Lead at TUM
- Memberships: GI, Frauencomputernetz and ECSO
- RDMSM Quote: Precision in research data management is as crucial as in coding for security. One flaw, and the system's integrity could be compromised.
- Success Story: Successfully thwarted a major cyber-attack on her university's research data servers by implementing a cutting-edge encryption protocol.
- Failure Story: Overlooked a small flaw in an otherwise robust security system, which led to a minor data leak. This experience reinforced her commitment to thoroughness in RDSM.
- With RDSM:
 - Striving to integrate best practices in RDSM into the core of cybersecurity operations, ensuring that every team member is equipped with the knowledge and tools to protect sensitive data.
 - Aims to teach and mentor students and staff about the importance of RDM, advocating for its role in protecting academic integrity.
 - Leading initiatives to create secure services for data sharing and collaboration across research institutions, enhancing the security infrastructure for collective defines against cyber threats.
- Help to address RDSM:
 - Ongoing professional development opportunities in the latest RDSM and cybersecurity trends.
 - Investment in state-of-the-art security software that aligns with the latest RDSM standards.
 - Collaboration with international cybersecurity experts to develop a global RDSM framework.

Persona: Martin Frings

- Holds a Master degree in Geography / Sports.
- A teacher at High School.
- RDMSM Quote: I need legal advice first.

- A politician who needs to be convinced about the necessary preservation of the Nationalpark Eifel

Persona: Martin Schneider

- Holds a Ph.D. in Computer Science with Data Science specialization.
- Head of Data Compliance at Auto Tech Data Systems, Munich, Germany.
- Memberships: IAPP, ADCB, GI and Special Interest Group on Data Science.
- RDSM Quote: In the interconnected world of automotive data, compliance is not just about following rules; it's about ensuring trust in every byte of data we collect and process.
- Academic goals: establish industry-leading standards for location data management in the automotive sector and to spearhead initiatives for global data compliance.
- Failure stories: Early in his career, he faced a setback when a project ran afoul of GDPR regulations due to poor data handling practices, which taught him the importance of robust RDM protocols.
- Success Story: Development of a compliance framework that was adopted across multiple departments, leading to a significant reduction in data breaches.
- With RDSM:
 - He is dedicated to teaching his colleagues about the importance of data compliance, and how it can be implemented without hindering innovation.
 - He is also involved in developing services and tools that facilitate secure and compliant data sharing between departments and with external partners.
- Help to address RDSM:
 - Access to advanced tools for real-time monitoring of data compliance.
 - Regular training sessions for staff on new data protection laws and regulations.
 - A cross-departmental committee dedicated to discussing and implementing RDM best practices.
 - Partnerships with technology providers to stay ahead of the curve in data security and compliance.